

Pressure Sore Risk Assessment among Nurses Working in Ekiti State University Teaching Hospital, Ado Ekiti, Nigeria

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Abstract:

Pressure ulcers (PU) may be defined as “ischemic soft tissue injuries resulting from pressure, usually over bony prominences. The study aims to investigate Pressure Sore Risk Assessment among nurses in EKSUTH. A cross sectional descriptive survey design was adopted among one hundred and fifty eight (158) Nurses who met the inclusion criteria and participated in the study. Ethical approval and informed consent of participants was obtained before data collection using a structured standardized adapted questionnaire. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the data collected while inferential techniques involving chi-square was used to determine the relationship between the variables. The result revealed good knowledge of pressure ulcer risk assessment, 67.7% scored eight and above. Only 32.3% scored below mean mark of eight. The only null hypothesis was not rejected. It was therefore concluded that the EKSUTH nurses have good knowledge on pressure ulcer risk assessment. It was recommended among others that guidelines on pressure ulcer prevention should be made available for nurses.

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Introduction

Pressure ulcers also known as decubitus ulcers are injury that erode the skin and underlying tissue when areas of skin is constantly placed under constant pressure for certain period of time causing tissue ischemia, cessation of nutrition and oxygen supply to the tissues and eventually tissue necrosis (Bhattacharya & Mishra, 2015). Some studies revealed that the overall knowledge is appropriate while others showed that the knowledge about pressure ulcers is adequate.

There are several factors that contribute to pressure ulcer development. These factors are divided into intrinsic and extrinsic factors (Ferri, 2017). Intrinsic factors include advanced age, immobility, dehydration, co morbidities, impaired sensory perception, altered tissue perfusion, malnutrition, anemia, organ system failure, and infections. Extrinsic factors include intensity and duration of pressure, friction, shearing, and maceration (Ferri, 2017). Nurses' knowledge and practice are also viewed as extrinsic factors for pressure injury development; this is because, even if the prevention of pressure ulcers is seen as a multidisciplinary responsibility, nurses generally play essential roles in its prevention (Ferri, 2017).

Knowledge has a direct impact on a nurse's attitudes towards PU; that is, a mindset which is significantly associated with the application of acceptable PU prevention techniques (Cox & Schallorm, 2017). Knowledge deficit can often be a significant cause leading to the development of PU. Thus, critical care nurses need ongoing education and training about PU prevention (Galvao et al., 2017). The findings showed that 57 (8.9%) patients developed PU during their stay in ICU. Grade I (33%) and grade IV (12.2%) ulcers accounted for the highest and lowest frequencies of PU, respectively. According to the American Nurses Association (ANA), pressure ulcer prevention is primarily a nursing responsibility though it is a multidisciplinary activity (NPUAP, 2019).

Lack of knowledge and skills in prevention of pressure ulcer contributes greatly to the occurrence or poor healing of the wound (García-Fernández et al., 2014). Knowledge, attitudes and skills are necessary to provide effective health care. Literature about the knowledge of health care providers towards pressure ulcers prevention is inconsistent. Some studies revealed that the overall knowledge is appropriate while others showed that the knowledge about pressure ulcers is adequate (Clark et al., 2017; Ahn et al., 2016).

A targeted preventive approach will be less costly than one that is focused on treating already established ulcers. Lack of knowledge and skills, and negative attitudes in PU prevention contributes significantly to the occurrence or worsening of PU. Raising nurses' knowledge about PU prevention among nurses not only increases the quality of PU care but also reduces hospital stays, and the number of patients suffering from this condition.

Knowledge deficit can often be a significant cause leading to the development of PU; thus, Critical Care Nurses' (CCNs) need ongoing education and training about PU prevention (Fletcher 2019). Several studies revealed that shortage of supplies for pressure ulcer management and prevention and shortages of human resource for health, particularly nurses, were the most cited barriers to carrying out appropriate pressure ulcer management (Ebi et al., 2017). Patients with PU generally have more additional diseases; PU is, at best, only a weak predictor of death. The Braden Scale for predicting pressure ulcer risk is a tool that was developed in 1987 by Barbara Braden and Nancy Bergstrom. The purpose of the scale is to help health professionals, especially nurses, assess a patient's risk of developing a pressure ulcer (Ebi et al., 2017). Therefore, this study investigated pressure sore risk assessment and

preventive practices among nurses working in Ekiti State University Teaching Hospital, Ado-Ekiti. Specifically, the study examined the knowledge level of nurse on pressure ulcer risk assessment.

Methods and Materials

This study adopted a descriptive cross sectional survey design to assess level of knowledge of pressure ulcer risk assessment and preventive practices among nurses in Ekiti State University Teaching Hospital, Ado Ekiti, Ekiti State Nigeria. Purposive sampling technique was used to select 10 unit in the hospital based on duration of admission, and systematic sampling method was use to select 158 respondents from the professional nurses in the wards of Ekiti State University Hospital, Ado Ekiti, Ekiti State. A closed structured questionnaire was adapted from Blenman et al., (2017), test-retest was used to ascertain the stability using Pearson Product Moment Correlation while the internal consistency was determined using Cronbach Alpha method. Descriptive and inferential statistics was used to analyze the data collected from the respondents.

Data was collected, analyzed and interpreted with SPSS version 23. Frequency tables for all questions were produced to identify missing information, detecting entry errors, and checking for inconsistencies. Mean and standard deviation of respondents' knowledge of pressure ulcer risk assessment were calculated, probability $P < 0.05$ was taken as the minimum level of significance. The descriptive statistics were used to summarize the data collected. Inferential techniques involving chi-square was used to determine the relationship between the variables.

Results

Table 1: Respondents' Socio Demographic Data

20-27	19	12.0
28-35	37	23.4
36-43	66	41.8
44-51	32	20.3
52-59	4	2.5
Total	158	100.0
Single	31	19.6
Married	121	76.6
Divorced	6	3.8
Total	158	100.0
Christianity	136	86.1
Islam	22	13.9
Total	158	100.0
Diploma	107	67.7
First degree	50	31.6
Msc	1	.6
Total	158	100.0
1-5	24	15.2
6-10	46	29.1
11-15	27	17.1

16-20	40	25.3
21-25	14	8.9
26 and above	5	3.2
Total	156	98.7
Male Medical Ward	21	13.3
Special Care Baby Unit	18	11.4
Gynecological ward	13	8.2
Intensive Care Unit	13	8.2
Psychiatric ward	17	10.8
Children ward	16	10.1
Female Surgical Ward	19	12.0
Antenatal ward	9	5.7
Male Surgical ward	16	10.1
Female Medical ward	16	10.1
Total	158	100.0

The Table 1 depicted the socio-demographic data of the participants, the majority of the nurses were found to be between age 36 and 43 years with value of 66 (41.8%) and very few were between the age of 52 and 59 years. Majority 121 (76.6%) were married and only 6 (3.8%) were divorced. About 136 (86.1%) were Christians and about 107 (67.7%) attained diploma as the highest level of education. About 46 (29.1%) nurses had spent between 6 and 10 years in service while only 5 (3.2%) had spent 26 years and above in service. Male medical ward (MMW) has the highest number of participants 21 (13.3%) followed by female surgical ward (FSW) with 19 participants and SCBU with 18 participants while ante natal ward (ANW) had the lowest participants 9 (5.7%).

Table 2: Knowledge Level of Nurses on PU Risk Assessment

	KNOWLEDGE				Knowledge Level	Mean	Standard Deviation
	Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative Percentage			
2.00	1	.6	.6	.6	Poor	8.0380	1.85763
3.00	3	1.9	1.9	2.5	Knowledge		
4.00	5	3.2	3.2	5.7	e		
5.00	10	6.3	6.3	12.0	(17.7%)		
	9	5.7	5.7	17.7			
	23	14.6	14.6	32.3	Good		
	31	19.6	19.6	51.9	knowledge		
	34	21.5	21.5	73.4	(82.3%)		
	42	26.6	26.6	100.0			
Total	158	100.0	100.0				

In Table 2, it was shown that 42 participants got all the marks correctly, while 28 (17.7%) had poor knowledge and 130 (82.3%) had good knowledge. However, the mean mark was 8.0380 with standard deviation of 1.85763. Only 51 (32.3%) scored below mean mark of eight. Therefore, 107 (67.7%) scored eight and above. It implies that the nurses are well knowledgeable about pressure ulcer risk assessment.

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between the level of academic qualification and knowledge of pressure ulcer risk assessment

Table 3: Chi-square showing relationship between knowledge and Educational Qualifications

		Knowledge		Total	χ^2	df	Sig	Remark
		Poor	Good					
Highest level of education	Diploma	18	89	107	4.705	2	0.095	Not sig
	First degree	9	41	50				
	MSc	1	0	1				
Total		28	130	158				

$P > 0.05$ df = degree of freedom; χ^2 = Chi-square; sig = Significance

Table 3 revealed that the null hypothesis was not significant ($\chi^2 = 4.705$, $df = 2$, $p = 0.095 > 0.05$), hence the null hypothesis is not rejected. The implication of this result is that there was no significant association between level of education of nurses and their knowledge on pressure ulcer risk assessment.

Discussion

The findings revealed that from 158 participants, only 28 (17.7%) had poor knowledge while the remaining 130 (82.3%) had good knowledge. It implies that the nurses are well knowledgeable about pressure ulcer risk assessment. This was at variance with the studies of Ingwu et al., (2019) and Clark et al. (2019) who submitted that nurses have poor knowledge on patient ulcer risk assessment. However, the result of this study agreed with the studies of Haesler and Carville (2015) and Esan et al. (2018) that nurses scored above average on questions on pressure ulcer risk assessment. The result confirmed that there was no significant relationship between knowledge of nurses and their educational attainment this outcome was not aligned with the findings of Esan et al. (2018) that pronounced that educational status of nurses significantly associated with knowledge on prevention of pressure ulcer.

Conclusion

The study concluded that the sampled EKSUTH nurses have knowledge on pressure ulcer risk assessment. The relationship between educational qualifications and levels of knowledge of EKSUTH nurses are not statistically significant.

Recommendations

Based on the findings from this study, the following are recommended:

1. Guidelines on pressure ulcer prevention should be made available.
2. Uncooperative patients should counseled about dangers associated with pressures ulcer
3. Nurses should be encouraged to prioritize their activities on the wards so that adequate time would be allotted to pressure ulcer assessment and prevention

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